
THE PRACTICAL ASPECT OF DESIGNING A TEXT IN A CHINESE SPEAKING AUDIENCE

Antsiferova N.B.,

*Candidate of Philological Sciences
Transbaikal State University*

Zvezdina Y.V.

*Candidate of Philological Sciences
Transbaikal State University*

Abstract

The article is devoted to the familiarity of foreign students with the tactics (self-identification, self-presentation) and strategies of the text. Attention is paid to the importance of the text in meeting the key communicative needs (contact-establishing, informational and influencing). The authors of the article offer productive tasks for the formation of speech tactics in teaching Chinese speaking student.

Keywords: Russian as a foreign language, text, Chinese speaking philology students, secondary linguistic personality.

Interest in implementation of various strategies in discourse appeared in the second half of the 20th century with the development of communicative linguistics. To date, the subject of research is strategies in the text of various styles and genres [Klushina], including the works of art [Pelevin]. Teaching competent text design is essential component of teaching Russian. The main goal in comprehending a foreign language is to learn to understand the main idea of the analyzed discourse and master the methods of successful text production for solving communicative tasks. It is particularly the necessity of finding solutions of communicative tasks when interacting in a group is recognized as the main trigger for the development of language, which is proved by the data of modern research [Benítez-Burraco]. Thus, the familiarity of foreign students with the tactics and strategies of the text are relevant at all stages of learning.

As a rule, the motivation for learning a foreign language is the desire to get a well-paid job, possibly in the country of the target language, which requires attending job interviews and meeting with a wide range of people. To successfully pass the job interview the candidate must master various tactics of the self-presentation strategy. Aside from that self-presentation is mandatory when meeting people, visiting various types of institutions, establishing friendly relations and business contacts. The first tactic, that a foreign student masters, can be defined as a tactic of self-identification, in particular when a person gives minimal information about oneself while meeting people – a full name or just a first name. The second tactic of self-presentation, which must be mastered by a foreign student, is defined as positive self-appraisal, namely when a person can describe one's personal and professional qualities.

The main issue of Chinese students studying Russian is inability to distinguish between the emotional-expressive peculiarity of words and expressions as well as a lack of comprehension of the influence of national mentality on the selection of vocabulary for a particular situation. Subsequently, in Russian culture it is not customary to speak about oneself in a superlative degree or emphasize one's uniqueness, therefore the lexeme "smart" is not used in the resume for describing merits,

being replaced by euphemisms: "I am a quick learner", "I like to improve my qualification".

The system of tasks aimed at mastering these tactics is a necessary component at all stages of teaching Russian as a foreign language.

Let us consider how the abovementioned principles and features of working with the texts of different types are implemented in the process of teaching Russian to Chinese students enrolled for field of study "Philology" at Transbaikal State University.

Students study the production of texts about themselves and their social status in their first year in the framework of the discipline "Foreign language (Russian)". Despite the fact that this topic is considered easy in absentia, even students who already speak Russian as part of the first certification level of the State Testing System (STSRFL-1) face difficulties of different types. Thus, 100% of them, at the first stages of learning self-presentation and appeal to the interlocutor are influenced by the traditions of the native languages. Firstly, in China, addressing a person and introducing the first and second names or a surname and a job position must be voiced, for example: "Hello, teacher Wang!", and according to this pattern Chinese students build Russian phrases: "Hello, teacher Ivanov", "Teacher Ivanov, I have a question".

Secondly, due to the absence of patronymics in Chinese language, students find it difficult to master their use in Russian. Replying to the question: "How is it more convenient for you to address a person in Russia in a formal setting?" A. By name and patronymic, B. By last name, C. By last name and job position, D. By job position E. By name and job position, F. Other" none of the interviewed students chose option A. Students explain this by the fact that Russian middle names are very difficult to remember and there is a fear of making a mistake in their declension. Teachers of Russian as a foreign language devote a lot of time to developing the ability to use Russian names, surnames and patronymics. At the same time, for about 10-20% of foreigner graduates of bachelor's programs can make mistakes in the use of patronymics or try to build communication without them.

Thirdly, introducing themselves Chinese students do not highlight the difference between their first and last names, voicing and using them as a kind of “monolith” according to the national tradition, which confuses native Russian speakers. Answering the question: “What is your name?” the Chinese student replies telling the name and surname: “Liu Guoping”, it is customary to tell only the name. To the following question: “What is your surname?” the student replies “Liu” which may give the impression that the foreigner’s name is Liu Liugopin. This clash of cultural traditions leads to mistakes in documentation. Chinese students need to be taught to explain their personal information: “My name is Liu Guopin. Liu is my surname, Guopin is my name. Please, call me Liu Guopin.”

Forthly, when studying in Russia and at home (if there are Russian teachers on the course), Chinese students, according to established tradition, choose Russian names, which sometimes accompany them for many years, especially if after graduating from the university the graduate gets a job in Russian-Chinese company. Thus, a Chinese woman can introduce herself as follows: “My name is Masha Wang.” The problem is that students, who got used to their “own” Russian names, transfer it to official documents: applications, petitions, practice reports, resumes, bank transfer forms, etc. That is why, when teaching students from China, the teacher usually monitors the accuracy of paperwork and reminds students about the inadmissibility of entering aliases and nicknames in a formal writing style.

Teaching foreigners to the tactics of self-introduction, it is necessary to remind the audience of students about the rule of relevance: different situations require different information to be reported. Among peers in particular students can only tell the name, but a conversation with a representative of administration, as an example, requires reporting information about the name, surname and place of study (faculty, course, group). A foreigner in Russia must be ready to indicate one’s age, nationality, marital and social statuses (studying or working). In Russia it is not customary to ask unfamiliar people about sexual orientation, political preferences and religion, but such questions are possible in friendly relations, which the teacher should warn foreign students about so that they are not embarrassed and

offended by such questions from Russian friends. To develop communication skills within the framework of this strategy, students are offered to 1) compose texts about themselves in various communication situations (meeting classmates, meeting a peer in a university library, meeting colleagues at a new job, meeting a head of a company or a business partner); 2) analysis of adapted and authentic self-presentation texts in Russian; 3) the study of the norms of etiquette while meeting new people.

Another self-presentation tactic is positive feedback. A foreign student should be able to present one’s strengths not only orally but also in writing, for example, during a job interview or writing a resume. To practice this tactic, students are offered the following tasks: 1) writing a resume using various templates; 2) analysis of a third-party resume from the position of an HR manager (would you accept this candidate for a vacant position? Why?); 3) staging of the interview; 4) work with lexical material (selection of euphemisms, compilation of antonymic pairs and synonymous series); 5) studying of the rules of business etiquette.

Without sufficient knowledge of speech tactics, it is impossible to solve communication issues and understand audiovisual texts adequately in case if relying on printed text is not available, for example, while watching movies in Russian, when it is necessary to decode the dialogues and polylogue of characters.

References

1. Benítez-Burraco A., Progovac L. A Four-Stage Model for Language Evolution Under The Effects of Human Self-Domestication // *Language & Communication*. 2020. T. 73. p. 1–17
2. Klushina N.I., Nikolaeva A.V., Liulikova A.V., Selezneva L.V., Skorokhodova E.Y., Tortunova I.A. Language use Nowadays In Russian Communication: Specifics and Trends // *Language and Dialogue*. 2019. No 3. T. 9. p. 444–470
3. Pelevin N.N. Author’s strategies of cognitive and communicative activity as a factor of text formation in scientific and artistic discourses. Abakan: Khakas Publishing House. State un. of N.F. Katanova, 2008. P. 151.